

A Poetic Cyber-Quest

Carole Collet, Central Saint Martins College of Art and Design, University of The Arts, London – UK

Abstract:

Throughout the 20th century, the relationship between textiles and architecture has often tilted back and forth. From celebrated rich and decorative cloth to purely functional fabrics, textiles in the home have been cherished as much as dismissed. The rapid emergence of intelligent textiles and ambient computing is once more challenging our use and perception of domestic textiles. As much as providing an open door to a brand new territory, these new technologies have often led to the development of high-tech and stereotypical “future” aesthetics. The likes of Phillips and Orange Future Homes propose a technologically - led design approach which ignores the creative and emotional potential of textiles.

This presentation will propose a body of textile work, which explores a more poetic and narrative-driven use of smart technologies. The most recently exhibited work was developed for “Remote Home”, and was presented at the Science Museum, London as well as at e-culture fair in 2003.

Keywords: Intelligent textiles, Architecture, Emotion, Narrative, Poetics, Home.

Design practice and research interest:

The main aim of the “Poetic Cyber Quest” is to explore the innovative potential of the use of textiles for the living environment within the context of emerging new geographies for the domestic space. An investigation into materials, processes, and new technologies will lead to questioning and repositioning textiles, furnishings and furniture design within the domestic space.

The design work is influenced by socio-cultural and technological shifts which can lead to a more sustainable future. Through producing conceptual work and exploring various design scenarios this research project intends to stretch the definition and understanding of “home”. This work will ultimately lead to innovative design products (furnishings, furniture, and intelligent products) for a new marketplace.

Although new technologies play a key role in the shaping of the project, the outcome focuses on a “human conscious” and somewhat poetic approach.

Research includes an investigation of various disciplines such as: textiles, architecture, interactive design, material sciences, new technologies (ambient computing, bio-mimicry, nano-technology), sociology, anthropology, fashion and art.

Design rationale:

The 21st century marks the beginning of a new paradigm for the domestic space. Three major issues will be affecting the way we frame and experience our domestic life: demographic changes, new technologies and materials, and sustainable practices.

“At the outset of the twentieth century, 10% of the population lived in cities. In 2000 around 50% of the world population lives in cities”, (Koolhaas 2000:2).

In London, “it is estimated that by 2020 almost four in ten homes will be occupied by single people. Of approximately five million new homes, 80% will be for people who live alone” (Foresight, 2000).

In the past decade we have experienced a drastic increase in urban population. We have now reached a stage wherein more people live in urban environment than in rural environment on a global scale. On a socio-cultural level, this shift creates new scenarios for living and new possibilities for design.

At the same time, the constant drive for technological innovation is rapidly affecting our selves, our lifestyles and our relationships to objects. Internet technology has enabled us to open our homes to the entire world, thus generating a more fluid sense of geographical boundaries. But if currently most of our experience of the virtual world takes place via screens and keyboards, we are now embarking on the next technological step; that of living with intelligent social objects. For instance, sensor devices and radio tagging technologies enable us to generate new experiences with our surrounding physical space. New meanings and new expectations will derive from these intelligent products and interfaces.

Andrea Saveri from the Institute of the Future (2003) also argues that “rather than experiencing the virtual world in a series of discrete episodic interactions, we will have a

world of ongoing or persistent experience...we move from experiencing discrete interactions to forms of ongoing presence. This adds the dimension of continuity to our daily practices.”

As new technologies and new social contexts arise, different social boundaries emerge, thus demanding a new approach to design. The meaning of “home” and the way we interact with it today is being transcended. A new design paradigm is ahead of us as the notions of time, place, identity, virtual and real relationships with the world are changing.

John Berger argues that “ Home is represented not by a house, but by a practice or a set of practices. Everyone has his own. These practices, chosen and not imposed, offer in their repetition, transient as they may be in themselves, more permanence, more shelter than any lodging. Home is no longer a dwelling but the untold story of a life being lived.” (Berger, Interior View n13, p 103)

When home becomes the “untold story of a life being lived”, it symbolises a new territory where architecture meets emotions, where new technologies can enhance human interactions. This is where textiles can assume a new role as a smart interface as much as a carrier of emotional values. Textiles have always been associated with our domestic rituals and our intrinsic experience of home but throughout the 20th century, the relationship between textiles and architecture has often swung back and forth. From celebrated rich and decorative cloth to purely functional fabrics, textiles in the home have been cherished as much as dismissed.

The rapid emergence of intelligent textiles and ambient computing is once more challenging our use and perception of domestic textiles. As much as providing an open door to a brand new territory, these new technologies have often led to the development of high-tech and stereotypical “future” aesthetics. The likes of Phillips and Orange Future Homes propose a technologically - led design approach which ignores the creative and emotional potential of textiles.

“The next generation of technology will speak to us, understand us and perceive our behaviours. It will enter every home and office and intercede between us and much of the information and experience we receive. The design of such intimate technology is an aesthetic issue as much as an engineering one. We must recognise this if we are to

understand and choose what we become as a result of what we have made” (Myron Krueger, 1977)

The “poetic cyber quest” is ultimately aiming at mapping out new territories where textiles have a leading role in redefining our intimate and emotional relationship with “smart homes”.

Design practice presentation:

The presentation will focus on the design work developed for “Remote Home”, a collaborative design project between The Interactive Institute, Sweden and Central Saint Martins College of Art and Design. The project is initiated by Tobi Schneidler from the Smart Studio, (Interactive Institute), and was produced for the international symposium: user_mode, Emotion & Intuition in Art & Design, held at Tate Modern, London in May 2003.

The project was exhibited simultaneously at the Science Museum in London and Raumlabor Gallery, Berlin. “Remote Home, One home, Two Cities, was also invited to be exhibited at e-culture fair in October 2003.

Figure 1, “Remote Home”, Science Museum, London, May 2003

Figure 2, “Remote Home” Raumlabor, Berlin 2003

Using Internet gateway technology, two prototype apartments were remotely designed and connected to respond to the presence and movement of their inhabitants.

The furniture and wall coverings physically transformed themselves in a symbiotic fashion and reacted to the absence or presence of their inhabitants.

The project focused on physical and emotional interactions as opposed to visual interfaces and connections. It aimed at creating a sense of poetics; where “home” is alive and comes to life only through the actions and rituals of its inhabitants. The domestic space becomes an extension of the body. Both flats were fitted with sensory and kinetic devices which enabled their inhabitants to share a sense of being together, connected beyond geographical boundaries.

The “Busy bench” is reacting to someone sitting down on the connected bench in Berlin. The bench changes shape to signal that someone is already using the bench, even though it is in the Berlin Home. Therefore one cannot sit down in London. This design effectively demonstrates possible interactions between remote flatmates.

Figure 3, Busy bench: still

Figure 4, Busy bench in movement

“Remote Home” is an interactive architectural proposal marrying textiles and new technologies to trigger a more emotive design response. The choice of materials and shapes reflects the desire to enhance a human and sensual exchange. From hand-knitted textiles to smart fabrics, the textile furniture explores the semiotic values of tactility, craft and the “hand-made” to counterbalance the symbolic values of high technologies and cyber-aesthetics. The sense of touch is highlighted both in the knitted cloth and the screen- printed wall panels.

Figure 5.a, Detail of the screen-printed wall panels

Figure 5.b

“The Kinetic Wall”

This wall bulges outwards and inwards in reaction to movements occurring in each apartment. The wall becomes more or less agitated depending on the scale of activity in the “Remote Home”.

Figure 6, wall in movement

Figure 7, wall in movement

Figure 8, “The remote bag and textile banners”

The bag designed by Steffi Schneider, keeps you connected to both homes, in London and Berlin via a wireless device. Vibration and light signals indicate when someone is home in London or Berlin. The bag is also connected to a set of textile banners which change colour when someone is leaving home in the remote apartment.

Figure 9

Figure 10

This thermochromic printed panel changes colour to indicate the absence or presence of an inhabitant in the remote apartment. Here, the same panel indicates someone is home in Berlin (on the left) and changes colour when someone leaves (on the right)

The project was successful in producing for the first time a remote live connection between two apartments where furniture and furnishings responded to each other as well as to the remote home inhabitants. Visitors of both exhibitions expressed their surprise as much as their desire for responsive and smart products which propose a different aesthetic and create a

more intimate sense of home. With increasing numbers of long distance relationships, this project proposes a new kind of symbolic and emotional exchange between partners, friends or family.

Credits:

Project team:

Smart Studio/Interactive Institute:

Tobi Schneidler, Architect and Project Manager

Magnus Jonsson , Engineer Fredrik Petersson, Engineer

Erik Grönvall, Programmer,

Stefanie Schneidler, Fashion designer Adam Somlai Fischer, Architect

Central Saint Martins College of Art and Design, University of the Arts, London

Carole Collet, Textile Designer, Course Director, MA Textile Futures

Tricia Austin, co-curator, user_mode Symposium

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Carole Collet MA (France) (UK): Carole Collet is trained as a textile designer. She is currently a senior lecturer and a researcher at Central Saint Martins College of Art and Design, London where she is the Course Director of the MA Textile Futures course. Her current academic research focuses on creating innovative textiles for the domestic environment.

She has recently exhibited work as part of “Remote Home” at the Science Museum, London and at e-culture fair, Amersdam (2003). A collection of smart cushions, and TV remote control cushions were produced in collaboration with Brunel University, Design For Life Department and exhibited at Avantex Trade Fair, Germany (2002). Her work has also been included as part of group shows in “Dirty washing” and “Design Against Crime” at the Design Museum, London and Zeus Gallery, Milano Furniture Fair (2001).